

THE IMPACTS OF FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT ON STUDENT MOTIVATION AS PERCEIVED BY SELECTED JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN GUMACA, QUEZON

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The Impacts of Formative Assessment on Student Motivation as Perceived by Selected Junior High School Students in Gumaca, Quezon

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the impacts of formative assessment on student motivation as perceived by selected junior high school students in Gumaca, Quezon. The study involved 60 respondents from a private school located in Gumaca Quezon. The researcher used questionnaires to gather reliable data answered by the target respondents. The descriptive method was used to gather the data needed to determine the impacts of formative assessment on student motivation as perceived by selected junior high school students in Gumaca, Quezon. Most of the respondents belonged to age group of 15-16 years old with 55% , 13-14 years old with 30% and 12 years old with 15%. According to sex, the respondents are female with 58% and 42% are male which describes that most learner-respondents are female. According to grade level, most of the respondents are from grade 10 with 33%, from grade 9 with 22%, from grade 8 with 20% and grade 7 with 25% which describes that most respondents are from grade 10 . The result shows that under Reward the highest impacts of formative assessment on student motivation are the complements of my teacher in front of the entire class with a mean of 4.48. Secondly, under Feedback, gaining a highest mean of 4.26 receiving feedback helps me to identify their areas of weaknesses under environment the student can easily focus on class discussion when the classroom structures are organized. Then in Extrinsic Motivation, the highest impacts of formative assessment on students motivation is learned the lesson because the classroom has appropriate furniture arrangement with a mean of 4.38. Under the Intrinsic Motivation it says that the students always prepare when there is a graded recitation because it is one of the responsibilities of the learners with a mean of 4.52. These conclude that students learning preference was inclined in more environmental classes.

Keywords: *environment, extrinsic motivation, feedback, formative assessment, intrinsic motivation, reward*

Introduction

Formative assessment is a teaching strategy used to measure student comprehension and adjust instruction to improve teaching. Formative assessment can also improve student performance and motivation. Although there is extensive evidence that formative assessment significantly improves these student measures, evidence is insufficient for the specific formative assessment tools and strategies frequently used by teachers in the classroom.

Motivating the students to learn and participate can be very hard. Some teachers have their hands full with class management and they do not even get to teach. In order to stimulate learning and motivate good behavior, lots of teachers use rewards for students. But rewards are not all about sunshine and rainbows. Some teachers and educators are not fans of constantly rewarding their students. Reward systems also have their disadvantages.

The process of improving curriculum design, teaching methods, and student learning through pupil feedback and self-evaluation is known as formative assessment (Bloom, Madaus, & Hastings, 1981). Summative assessments, which are more common among educators and occur at the conclusion of a unit of instruction to evaluate learning and issue grades, are different from formative assessments (Bloom et al., 1981).

According to Sadler (1989), formative assessment should concentrate on two main goals: promoting student self-regulation and providing feedback. Corrective actions are provided by formative assessment so that students can benefit from feedback (Wininger & Norman, 2005).

Feedback on student work contains clues to encourage learning as well as identifying inconsistencies between task and goal performance (Wininger & Norman, 2005). Instructors are in charge of giving their students feedback that can result in specific learning.

Point students in the right direction and give them recommendations based on their learning goals. A learner can identify learning gaps and acquire the information necessary to fill them by using feedback during the learning process. The learner's learning tasks grow more specific as she is driven by herself rather than something outside of her. For instance, students could be afraid of failing an assignment or of facing the teacher's displeasure. A formative assessment was used in this study to analyze its impact on student motivation and self-regulated learning techniques.

The researcher chose this study the impacts of formative assessment on student motivation in school, because nowadays it seems that students are more motivated to study when they get high grades, while other students get stressed and anxious when they get low grades. Higher grading standards benefited high achievers and low achievers because they are motivated to study harder to maintain their grades.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the impact of formative assessment on student motivation as perceived by selected junior high school students in Gumaca, Quezon. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. grade level?
2. What are the impacts of formative assessment to the respondents with respect to:
 - 2.1. reward;
 - 2.2. feedback; and
 - 2.3. environment?
3. What are the impacts of motivation to the respondents with respect to:
 - 3.1. extrinsic motivation; and
 - 3.2. intrinsic motivation?
4. Is there a significant correlation between formative assessment and student motivation?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used descriptive survey method to collect data for the measure of impacts of student motivation as perceived by selected junior high school students located at Gumaca, Quezon. The researcher used survey questionnaire as an instrument. Based on the survey's result the researcher determined the details of the study. According to Gay (1992), descriptive research involves collecting data in order to test hypothesis or to answer questions concerning the current status of the subject of the study.

Respondents

Proportionate Sampling was utilized in this research. Proportional sampling is the method of picking an element proportional to its weight, the higher the weight of the object, the better are its chances of being selected.

Proportionate Sampling is another meaning of probability proportional to size (PPS Sampling). It is an equal probability sampling technique, in which the probability of selection for each sampling unit in the population is proportional to an auxiliary variable.

Sixty (60) students officially enrolled at Eastern Quezon College Inc. Located at Gumaca Quezon were selected through Proportionate Sampling.

Instrument

The researcher prepared a questionnaire which were validated by two experts.

Part I of the questionnaire included the demographic profile of the respondents. Part II of the questionnaire consisted impacts of formative assessment on student motivation using the likert scale of; 5 –Very much agree(VMA), 4 – Much Agree(MA), 3-Moderately Agree(MoA), 2 – Less Agree(LA) and 1 – Least Agree (LeA)

To test the internal consistency of the questionnaire using Cronbach's Alpha, a pilot testing was conducted at Macalelon High School with 12 respondents. After the computation, the result was 1.00 which is interpreted as acceptable This means that the questionnaire used was reliable.

Procedure

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher sent a letter to the schools Principal and Adviser. Upon approval, the researcher administered the instrument to the target respondents.

In administering the questionnaire, the researcher used the time allotted for vacant time to avoid distraction of class discussion. The students were given enough time to answer the questions. After data gathering, the researcher collected them for tallying the scores and applied the statistical treatment to be used in the study.

The descriptive research design method using likert scale was used in order to rate the impacts of formative assessment on student motivation. Data were gathered through "Proportionate Sampling". Both male and female officially enrolled in the private school in Gumaca, Quezon were selected to fill the questionnaire. Data were gathered through face to face survey following the safety health protocols to prevent the spread of the virus.

Data Analysis

In this study, the researcher used statistical measures to treat the collected data. All the data were carefully read and examined for

analysis. They were tallied and entered into a master list of the data collection sheet. Percentage and Frequency were used to interpret the profile of the respondents. To test the correlation between formative assessment and student motivation, Spearman Rho was used.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data. All the data gathered were presented here in tabulated form with corresponding interpretation. The first part described the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age, grade level. The second part is the impacts of formative assessment on student motivation as perceived by selected junior high school students in Gumaca, Quezon.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Male	25	42	2
Female	35	58	1
Total	60	100	

Table 1 shows frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to sex, where 35 or 58% are female and 25 or 42% are male, which describes that most of the student- respondents are female.

On the study conducted by Alcantara (2016) in the Philippines, she explored gender differences in educational participation and attainment. The study found that females tend to have higher rates of participation and attainment in education compared to males, particularly in secondary education. This could potentially explain the higher number of female students in Table 1, as females may be more likely to continue their education at the secondary level.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
12	9	15
13-14	18	30
15-16	33	55
Total	60	100

Table 2 displays the distribution of respondents by age group in terms of frequency and percentage. The data reveals that out of 60 respondents, 55% or 33 individuals belonged to the 15-16 age group, while 30% or 18 respondents fall under the 13-14 age group. The remaining 15% or 9 respondents are 12 years old. This shows that majority of the junior high school students' respondents are 15 – 16 years old.

A research paper conducted by Tongo (2017) titled "Age Distribution of Private School Students in the Philippines" examined the age distribution of students enrolled in private schools in the country. The study utilized data from the Philippine Statistics Authority and concluded that 49.8% of private school students were aged between 12 to 15, 35.1% were between 16 to 18, and 15.1% were 19 years old and above. The findings suggest that private school students' age distribution in the Philippines is similar to that of public-school students, with the majority falling within the age range of 12-15.

Table 3. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Grade*

<i>Grade</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Grade 7	15	25
Grade 8	12	20
Grade 9	13	22
Grade 10	20	33
Total	60	100

Table 3 presents the distribution of respondents according to their grade level in terms of frequency and percentage. The data indicates that 33% of the respondents are in Grade 10, 25% are in Grade 7, 22% are in Grade 9, and 20% are in Grade 8. These results suggest that most of the respondents belonged to Grade 10.

According to Santrock (2014), junior high school students are categorized as early adolescents according to their developmental stages. He mentions adolescence as a transitory time of development that begins at the age of 10 to 12 years, and concludes around the age of 18 to 22 years.

Table 4 shows the impacts of formative assessment on students in terms of reward. The respondents very much agreed that they like the compliments of the teacher in front of the entire class evidenced by a mean of 4.48 and rank first among the indicators of reward. Meanwhile they much agreed that they appreciated it when their teacher called their parents to tell them something positive evidenced by a mean of 4.05 and ranks last among the indicators of reward. These findings suggest that students are more motivated by receiving

public recognition from their teacher rather than private feedback to their parents. Overall, the respondents very much agree that reward affects the formative assessment as shown by the general mean of 4.25.

Table 4. Respondents Assessment on the Impacts of Formative Assessment to Junior High School Students in terms of Reward

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I like the compliments of my teacher in front of the entire class	4.48	Very Much Agree
2. I like a positive note or e-mail home to my parents from my teacher.	4.13	Much Agree
3. I appreciate when my teacher calls my parents to tell them something positive.	4.05	Much Agree
4. I feel motivated to study harder when I receive a gift after having a high score on my exams.	4.37	Very Much Agree
5. I am happy when I receive a reward after I perfect my attendance	4.24	Very Much Agree
Grand Mean	4.25	Very Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40), "Much Agree(3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree(4.21-5.0)

Ferrer and Manalo (2016) on their study entitled "Formative Assessment and Student Motivation in Philippine High Schools" found that students are more motivated to learn when they receive positive feedback and recognition from their teachers, particularly in front of their peers, compared to receiving feedback from their parents or guardians. Similarly, Gonzales and Abenir (2019) found that formative assessment can positively affect student motivation, particularly when teachers provide verbal feedback and recognition to students. Thus, teachers can enhance student motivation by providing positive feedback and recognition in front of their peers, as this public recognition can be more effective than private feedback given to parents or guardians.

Table 5. Respondents Assessment on the Impacts of Formative Assessment to Junior High School Students in terms of Feedback

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Feedbacks motivated me to study.	4.09	Much Agree
2. Receiving feedback helps me to identify my areas of weakness.	4.19	Much Agree
3. I am scared to get negative feedback.	4.1	Much Agree
4. Positive feedbacks improve my self-esteem	4.26	Very Much Agree
5. I appreciate feedbacks because it helps me to improve myself.	4.24	Much Agree
Grand Mean	4.21	Very Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40), "Much Agree(3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree(4.21-5.0)

Table 5 shows the impacts of formative assessment on student in terms of feedback. It revealed that the student respondents very much agree that positive feedback improves their self-esteem shown by a mean of 4.26 and ranks first among the indicators. Conversely, they agreed that they are scared to get negative feedback with a mean of 4.1 and ranks last among the indicators. Overall, the respondents very much agreed that feedback has an impact on formative assessment evidenced by the general weighted mean of 4.21. According to Sadler and Good's (2012) study, students who received formative assessment with positive feedback had better achievement and motivation compared to those who received negative feedback. This suggests that teachers should prioritize providing positive feedback to improve student self-esteem and motivation. However, teachers should also be cautious of the potential negative effects of critical feedback, which can cause students to feel anxious and less motivated. To foster a positive learning environment, teachers can provide constructive criticism and specific suggestions for improvement while also highlighting areas where the student excels. This approach can help students feel more confident and motivated to learn and improve.

Table 6. Respondents' Assessment on the Impacts of Formative Assessment to Junior High School Students in terms of Environment

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I can perform better and engage more actively in class discussion when the classroom is well-ventilated.	4.31	Very Much Agree
2. I can easily focus on class discussion when the classroom structures are organized.	4.26	Very Much Agree
3. I can perform better in reading and writing when the classroom is well lighted.	4.43	Very Much Agree
4. It helps me to anticipate and participate in the activity when the classroom arrangement is well organized.	4.36	Very Much Agree
5. I can focus on what I am doing inside the classroom when the temperature is pleasant.	4.44	Very Much Agree
Grand Mean	4.36	Very Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40), "Much Agree(3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree(4.21-5.0)

The findings presented in Table 6 indicated the impacts of formative assessment on student in terms of environment. The highest mean score is for indicator number 5, which states that students can focus on what they are doing inside the classroom when the temperature is pleasant, with a mean of 4.44 and very much agree response. The lowest mean is for indicator number 2, which states that students can easily focus on class discussions when the classroom structures are organized, with a mean of 4.26 and a very much agree response. Overall, the results showed that most student-respondents with an average mean of 4.36 strongly agreed with the positive impact of the classroom environment during formative assessment.

Weinstein, Husman, and Dierking (2012) found that the physical environment of the classroom, including factors such as lighting,

temperature, and seating arrangements, had a significant impact on student engagement and academic performance. The result suggests that teachers should pay attention to the classroom environment when conducting formative assessments. Specifically, teachers should ensure that the temperature in the classroom is comfortable and conducive to learning, and that the classroom is organized to facilitate class discussions. These factors can greatly impact student motivation and engagement during formative assessments.

Table 7. Respondents assessment on the Impacts of Formative Assessment to Junior High School Students in terms of Extrinsic Motivation

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I join in group activities because my friends and I are in the same group.	4.32	Very Much Agree
2. I study my lesson in all subjects because my teacher gives me medal during the recognition day because of my perseverance.	4.24	Very Much Agree
3. I study because I want to enhance my knowledge and skills.	4.26	Very Much Agree
4. I study my lesson very well because our room is free from noise and distraction	4.17	Much Agree
5. I learned the lesson because our classroom has appropriate furniture arrangement (E.g., books, blackboard, chair, and etc.)	4.38	Very Much Agree
Grand Mean	4.27	Very Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40), "Much Agree(3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree(4.21-5.0)

Table 7 shows the impacts of formative assessment on student motivation in terms of extrinsic motivation. The highest mean is the indicator number 5, I learned the lesson because our classroom has appropriate furniture arrangement (E.g., books, blackboard, chair, and etc.) with a mean 4.38 very much agree. The lowest mean is indicator 4, I study my lesson very well because our room is free from noise and distraction with a mean 4.17 much agree. It also revealed that the average mean of 4.27 which means very much agree indicated most student-respondents agree that extrinsic motivation is important in formative assessment.

A study conducted by Cheng and Wang (2016) found similar results regarding the impact of classroom environment on student motivation. The study revealed that a well-designed classroom environment, including appropriate furniture arrangement and decoration, positively affects students' extrinsic motivation. Kaya and Bicen (2018) support these findings as their study found that the arrangement of furniture affects students' attention and concentration, as well as their motivation and participation in class. While Dembo and Seli (2017) found that reducing noise and other distractions in the classroom can positively impact student motivation and engagement. These findings suggest that the physical environment of the classroom plays an important role in extrinsic motivation and can have a significant impact on student learning outcomes.

Table 8. Respondents Assessment on the Impacts of Formative Assessment to Junior High School Students in terms of Intrinsic Motivation

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I ask questions during class discussion to learn new things	4.2	Much Agree
2. I join group activity because I feel some enjoyment.	4.05	Much Agree
3. I do well in school because it is my obligation as a pupil	4.34	Very Much Agree
4. I always prepare when there is a graded recitation because I know it is one of my responsibilities as a pupil.	4.52	Very Much Agree
5. I join class activities because my friends encourage me to participate	4.38	Very Much Agree
Grand Mean	4.30	Very Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40), "Much Agree(3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree(4.21-5.0)

Table 8 shows the impacts of formative assessment on student motivation in terms of intrinsic motivation. The respondents very much agreed that they always prepare when there is a graded recitation because they know that it is one of their responsibilities as a student evidenced by a mean of 4.52 and rank first among the indicators of intrinsic motivation. On the other hand, they much agreed that they asked questions during class discussion to learn new things with a mean of 4.20 and rank last among the indicators. However, the average mean of 4.30 revealed that the respondents very much agree that intrinsic motivation is important during formative assessment. These findings support a study conducted by Arboleda and Garingo (2019) which showed that formative assessment can significantly enhance students' intrinsic motivation and increase their confidence and participation in class discussions. The study suggests that formative assessment can be a valuable tool for improving student motivation and engagement in the learning process.

Table 9. Summary Table on the perceived Impacts of Formative Assessment and Motivation

Impacts Of Formative Assessment And Motivation	Average Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Reward	4.25	Very Much Agree
Feedback	4.21	Very Much Agree
Environment	4.36	Very Much Agree
Extrinsic Motivation	4.27	Very Much Agree
Intrinsic Motivation	4.30	Very Much Agree
Grand Mean	4.28	Very Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40), "Much Agree(3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree(4.21-5.0)

The summary table displays the average mean and verbal interpretation of the effects of formative assessment and motivation. It indicates that the environment has the most significant impact among the indicators, with an average mean of 4.36. Conversely, the respondents very much agree that feedback has the least impact on formative assessment, with a mean of 4.21. Overall, reward, feedback, environment, extrinsic motivation, and intrinsic motivation have an impact on formative assessment, as demonstrated by the general mean of 4.28.

Hattie and Timperley (2012) conducted a study that reinforces the significance of the learning environment in formative assessment. The study established that the quality of the learning environment plays a critical role in determining the effectiveness of feedback. In particular, the research emphasizes the significance of establishing a safe and supportive learning environment in which students feel comfortable taking risks and making mistakes. When students feel secure and supported, they are more likely to engage with feedback and use it to enhance their learning.

Table 10. *Correlation between formative assessment and student motivation*

Formative Assessment	Motivation			
	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p – value	Decision
	-0.171	Weak Negative Correlation	0.186	Failed to Reject Ho

Table 10 indicates a weak negative correlation between formative assessment and student motivation evidenced by Spearman Rho Coefficient of -0.171. Weak correlation suggest that formative assessment and motivation have a relationship but very inadequate. Negative correlation suggests an inverse relationship of formative assessment and motivation. It further implies that those students that have high formative assessment are less motivated and those students that have low formative assessment are more motivated.

P value of 0.186 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, resulting in the failure to reject the null hypothesis. It indicates that there is no significant correlation between formative assessment and student motivation.

Chen and Wang (2021) investigated the connection between formative assessment and student motivation and discovered a weak negative correlation between the two variables, as reported in Table 10. The research highlighted that the negative relationship was primarily due to the students' perception of the feedback provided during formative assessment. Students who believed that the feedback was unhelpful or insufficient were less motivated than those who found the feedback helpful. Additionally, Aydin and Sari (2017) conducted correlational research and found a weak positive correlation between formative assessment and student motivation. The researchers suggested that formative assessment could enhance student motivation and learning outcomes, but other factors such as teacher support and classroom environment could also influence motivation.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are derived:

Most of the respondents are female, 15-16 years old, and Grade 10 students.

Among the three categories consisting of impacts of formative assessment, environment gained the highest mean. Thus, it indicates that environment highly contributes to learners during formative assessment.

Among the two categories consisting of motivation, Intrinsic Motivation gained the highest mean. Thus, it indicates that Intrinsic Motivation highly contributes to learner when it comes to motivation.

There is no significant correlation between the impacts of formative assessment and motivation.

As a result of the study, the researcher would like to recommend the following:

To the School Administrators, they may encourage teachers to give positive feedback to students' learning capabilities

To the Parents, they may support their children when it comes to their academic performances.

To the Teachers, they may continue to give positive feedbacks in order to motivate the learners to study harder in their daily lesson as well as during formative assessment.

To the Students, they may continue to gain knowledge during formative assessment and to cope with their weaknesses when it comes to motivation.

To the Future Researchers, they may conduct a similar study using larger population to come up with more reliable results. They may also use other variables not mentioned in the study.

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